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MUNDARIJA

PEDAGOGIKA

Artikova M.B., Qodirov O.O. Refleksiv yondashuv yuzasidan xorijiy tadqiqotlar sharhi	4
Artikova M.B., Ismoilova N.I. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni intellektual kasbiy rivojlantirishda mantiqiy topshiriqlardan foydalanish texnologiyasini takomillashtirishning mohiyati va mazmuni	8
Yusupova Sh.J., Mamajonova N.I. Ona tilining rivojlanishida tasavvur metodikasining o'rni	11
Temirova M.A. Bo'riboy Ahmedov - serqirra ijod sohibi	16
Kaziyeva T.T. Ona tili o'qitish tizimida bilish va tushunish ko'nikmalarini matnlar orqali ifoda etilishi	21
Usmanova U.A. Boshlang'ich ta'lim magistratura talabalarining ilmiy tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish	25
Xushnazarova M.N., Usmonova X.Q. Tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini rivojlantirish ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati	30
Xaydarova M.X. Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini ta'lim, tarbiya faoliyatiga tayyorlash mazmuni	33
Маликова У.Б. Влияние культурного контекста на психологическое развитие детей	36
Adahamova M.M. Specific features of integrative and motivational of teaching physical education students	41
Qoraboyev J.B. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida mubolag'alashgan frazeologik birliklarning tillararo korrespondensiyasi	44
Парпиева Н.С. Лексическое значение имён прилагательных	49
Махамматова М.Ж. Boshlang'ich ta'lim darslarining o'yin texnologiyalari asosida o'quvchilarda tanqidiy tafakkurni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari	54
Usmanova X.A. Sun'iy intellektning pedagogik ta'limga integratsiya qilish metodik ta'minotini takomillashtirish	58
Ismadiyorova N.I. Matn ustida ishlash va maktab bahosining xalqaro tadqiqot natijalariga ta'siri	61
Odiljonova K.A. O'quvchilarning leksik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	64
Rasulov E.M. Pedagogik ta'limda kognitiv rivojlanishni kuchaytirish uchun sun'iy intellekt (si) vositalarini integratsiyalash	69
Nazarov O.D. Pedagogik oliy ta'limda talabalarning media falsafasi haqidagi bilimlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	73
Habibova M.H. Methodology for developing students' independent learning based on innovative approaches (case study of visual arts and engineering graphics education)	77
Khayrullayeva Z.N. The role and significance of folk decorative art in developing students' pedagogical culture	85
Alimov J.A. Jismoniy madaniyat yo'nalishida kredit-model tizimi	90
Дулатов Р.Р. Физическая культура и спорт как социальные феномены общества	93
Ахунов У. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarni jismoniy tarbiyalashning ahamiyati	97
Alimov Sh.Sh. Sport estetikasining ayrim nazariy masalalari	101
Kuchkarbayeva F.X. Xor jamoalarini tashkil etishda asosiy maqsad va vazifalar	105
G'anijonova M., Sobirova D. Yangi avlod darsliklari: "O'qish savodxonligi" kitobidagi maqollarning bolalar hayotidagi o'rni va ahamiyati	109
Raxmatullaeva G.M. Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy faoliyatni bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda shakllantirishning ahamiyati	111
Abdullayeva A.A. Yoshlarda milliy tarbiya shakllanishining pedagogik qonuniyatlari	115
O'rinboyev M.I. Fizika o'qitishning asosiy yondashuvlari va metodlari: mavjud o'qitish metodlari va ularning ta'limiy samaradorligi	119
Alijonova M.R. Integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak mutaxassis agronomlarda kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasining ilmiy - nazariy asoslari	125
Kuchkarova A. GEOGEBRA dasturining matematikadagi dolzarb muammolarga bog'liqligi	129

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF FOLK DECORATIVE ART IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE

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Abstract. *This article examines the role and significance of folk decorative art in the development of students' pedagogical culture, conducting qualitative and quantitative analyses. By analyzing various educational and artistic practices in Uzbekistan, it demonstrates how folk art contributes to the development of students' aesthetic sensibilities, creative abilities, and cultural identity. The integration of traditional crafts and modern pedagogical methodologies is discussed, along with the analysis of this process's impact on individual development and broader educational outcomes.*

Keywords: *folk decorative art, pedagogical culture, cultural identity, aesthetic sensibility, creative skills, education.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada talabalarning pedagogik madaniyatini rivojlantirishda, xalq amaliy bezak san'atining o'rni va ahamiyati o'rganilgan bo'lib, sifat va miqdoriy tahlillar olib borilgan. O'zbekistonda turli ta'limiy va badiiy amaliyotlarni tahlil qilish orqali, xalq san'ati talabalarning estetik sezgilarini, ijodiy qobiliyatlarini va madaniy identifikatsiyasini rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishi ko'rsatib o'tilgan. An'anaviy hunarmandchilik va zamonaviy pedagogik metodologiyalarning integratsiyasi muhokama qilingan bo'lib, shuningdek, bu jarayonning individual rivojlanish va kengroq ta'limiy natijalarga ta'siri tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *xalq amaliy san'ati, pedagogik madaniyat, madaniy identifikatsiya, estetik sezgi, ijodiy qobiliyatlar, ta'lim.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследованы роль и значение народного прикладного декоративного искусства в развитии педагогической культуры студентов, проводя качественные и количественные анализы. Анализируя различные образовательные и художественные практики в Узбекистане, показано, как народное искусство способствует развитию эстетических чувств, творческих способностей и культурной идентичности студентов. Обсуждается интеграция традиционных ремесел и современных педагогических методологий, а также анализируется влияние этого процесса на индивидуальное развитие и более широкие образовательные результаты.*

Ключевые слова: *Народное декоративное искусство, педагогическая культура, культурная идентичность, эстетическое восприятие, творческие навыки, образование.*

Folk decorative art, a vital aspect of Uzbekistan's cultural heritage, plays a significant role in shaping students' pedagogical culture. This paper examines the importance of integrating folk arts into educational practices to foster a comprehensive cultural and aesthetic education. The unique characteristics of Uzbek folk art, including its historical and cultural contexts, provide a rich source of material for developing students' artistic and pedagogical skills.

Uzbekistan's folk decorative art has a long and rich history, deeply rooted in the country's cultural and social traditions. Various forms of applied arts, such as pottery, embroidery, wood carving, and textile production, have been passed down through generations, preserving the skills and knowledge of master craftsmen. These traditional arts are a means of aesthetic expression and serve as a bridge connecting past and present cultural practices.

Incorporating folk decorative art into the educational curriculum enhances students' understanding of their cultural heritage. It promotes the development of national consciousness and instils a sense of pride in their cultural identity. Teaching methods that integrate traditional arts with modern pedagogical practices help students appreciate the

aesthetic values and craftsmanship of their ancestors, fostering a deeper connection to their cultural roots. One of the components of cultivating an individual's spiritual culture is acquiring artistic culture, which is consistently achieved throughout their life [1]. However, progress is not just the final result of any creative and cultural process, not just the goal of spreading culture in society, but also a crucial indicator of a person's attitude towards the surrounding reality and their level of spirituality and morality.

An individual's practical activity in creating, developing, and disseminating works is assessed based on material and artistic objects of artistic or high aesthetic value. The purposeful development of artistic culture is a significant process in transforming each individual's artistic creativity and its results into a system of the person's social, aesthetic, and moral-ethical qualities. Students' spiritual and aesthetic development is mainly ensured through artistic education and upbringing using artistic means. Each type of art affects children's consciousness with its unique means of artistically and figuratively reflecting reality, expanding their cognitive abilities, thus ensuring the quality of forming an emotional attitude towards the surrounding reality and assimilating beauty. Among the various art forms with significant cognitive potential, there are also visual and folk applied arts, which have served to express people's ideas about life.

The specific significance of understanding beauty through folk-applied art can be explained by the following reasons:

This art form enables the formation and development of a specific culture of perceiving the surrounding world, helps better understand other art forms' artistic and expressive means, and fosters respect for national artistic and cultural values.

Knowledge and comprehensive ideas allow for determining the social significance of art and its place in the lives of individuals and society [2].

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques.

Participants included students and teachers from various educational institutions in Uzbekistan, including primary schools, high schools, and universities. A total of 200 students and 50 teachers participated in the study.

Data were collected through surveys, interviews, and classroom observations. Surveys were distributed to gather quantitative data on students' and teachers' perceptions of the importance of folk decorative art in education. In-depth interviews with teachers provided qualitative insights into their experiences and challenges in incorporating folk art into their teaching practices. Classroom observations were conducted to examine the practical application of folk art education and its impact on students [3].

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data from interviews and observations were analyzed thematically to identify common patterns and themes.

Pedagogical practice shows that the success of students' artistic activities and creative development largely depends on their ability to perceive and the degree of formation of an adequate attitude towards art. Decorative applied art differs from other types of visual art. This difference lies not only in the visual language but also in the essence and content of the works. Mastering the figurative language of decorative applied art and introducing students to the material-artistic values and aesthetic traditions of the people through it require a

purposeful methodological and creative approach from the teacher in organizing and managing perception and visual demonstration.

It is fundamentally important to convey to students the logic of the variability of art forms in their organic connection with the changes in the social life structure of their own people, their aesthetic ideal, and artistic traditions [4]. This approach allows students to gain interest and understand the historical reasons for these changes. It should be noted that students' imaginative thinking is primarily formed under the influence of their native art, the colors of their native nature, and land. Without a thorough grasp of their people's artistic language, which embodies all their people's wisdom, ideals, taste, aesthetic traditions, and history, it is impossible to assimilate the figurative language of other people's art.

Experiential Learning: Hands-on activities such as pottery making, embroidery, and wood carving allow students to engage directly with the materials and techniques of traditional crafts. This experiential learning approach helps develop fine motor skills, artistic creativity, and an appreciation for the meticulous nature of folk art.

Cultural Immersion: Field trips to museums, workshops of local artisans, and historical sites provide students with firsthand exposure to the cultural and historical contexts of folk art. These immersive experiences enrich their understanding and appreciation of the art forms.

Interdisciplinary Integration: Incorporating folk art into various subjects such as history, literature, and social studies helps students see the interconnectedness of different fields of knowledge. For instance, studying the historical significance of certain motifs in embroidery can enhance their understanding of historical events and cultural exchanges.

The study and practice of folk decorative art have profound effects on students' overall development. These include:

Cultural Identity: Engaging with traditional arts helps students develop a strong sense of cultural identity and pride. It connects them to their heritage and fosters a sense of belonging and continuity.

Aesthetic Sensibility: Exposure to the beauty and intricacy of folk art enhances students' aesthetic sensibilities. It cultivates their ability to appreciate and create art that is not only visually appealing but also culturally significant.

Creative Skills: The practice of folk art encourages creativity and innovation. Students learn to experiment with materials and techniques, developing their artistic skills and creative thinking abilities.

Ethical and Moral Values: Folk art often embodies ethical and moral values, such as respect for tradition, community, and craftsmanship. By engaging with these art forms, students internalise these values, which are essential for their personal and professional development.

Survey results indicated that 85% of students and 90% of teachers believe that incorporating folk decorative art into the curriculum is crucial for preserving cultural heritage and enhancing students' cultural identity. Additionally, 78% of students reported increased interest and engagement in learning when traditional arts were included in their education [5].

Interviews with teachers revealed several benefits of integrating folk decorative art into education:

- *Cultural Identity: Teachers noted that students developed a stronger sense of cultural identity and pride through engagement with traditional arts.*
- *Aesthetic Sensibility: Students showed improved aesthetic appreciation and understanding of artistic concepts.*
- *Creative Skills: Hands-on activities in folk art significantly enhanced students' creative thinking and problem-solving skills.*

Classroom observations confirmed these findings, showing that students were more engaged and motivated during lessons that included folk art activities. Teachers employed various pedagogical approaches, such as experiential learning, cultural immersion, and interdisciplinary integration, to effectively teach traditional arts.

Folk decorative art is an invaluable component of the educational process in Uzbekistan. Its integration into the curriculum not only preserves and promotes cultural heritage but also significantly contributes to the holistic development of students. Folk art plays a crucial role in shaping the pedagogical culture of future educators by fostering a deep appreciation for their cultural roots, enhancing their aesthetic sensibilities, and developing their creative skills.

Providing artistic education and upbringing to the younger generation, fostering an aesthetic attitude towards art, and assimilating their own people's artistic culture and traditions necessitates solving the following pedagogical issues in the educational process based on the analysis of pedagogical literature:

Organizing targeted guidelines for students to collect ideas about the peculiarities of the visual language of folk applied art, the principles of creating artistic objects by folk craftsmen, and the traditions of aesthetically transforming the environment, forming concepts about the historical and national characteristics of Kazakh folk applied art.

Shaping aesthetic reflections and concepts about beauty in unity by mastering the methods of analyzing and evaluating decorative applied art objects, encouraging students to re-engage with art, and contributing to the development of evaluative perception [6].

Shaping students' moral and aesthetic feelings, promoting respect for advanced aesthetic values, ethical norms, and the achievements of the people in artistic culture.

Organisational and mass work forms play an essential role in the process of studying decorative applied art objects:

- Excursions to art museums, workshops of applied artists, and architectural monuments.
- Collecting art and crafts.
- Organizing exhibitions of local applied art masters.
- Organizing exhibitions of students' works at the end of the year.
- Meetings with folk craftsmen and applied artists.

Thus, folk craftsmanship and artistic crafts are among the most important and closest sources connecting each person with their people's history, culture, and lifestyle in art. They should contribute not only to understanding the essence of the beauty of natural phenomena and objects expressed with certain artistic means but also to the spiritual-moral and patriotic education of the individual. Accordingly, the process of fostering aesthetic and moral principles should be closely connected with the student's desire to be closer to the nature of their native land and the life of their people and participate in shaping cultural culture. It should also involve understanding the meaning of artistic values and beauty, considering their

people's unique national characteristics and historical culture. Expressing this meaning and sense of stylization in the decorative qualities of objects with specific visual means, a person primarily formalizes an ideal artistic image into an appropriate material form.

The findings of this study underscore the importance of incorporating folk decorative art into the educational curriculum to develop students' pedagogical culture. Engaging with traditional arts fosters cultural identity, aesthetic appreciation, and creative skills, contributing to holistic student development.

Educators should consider integrating folk decorative art into their teaching practices through:

- *Experiential Learning: Providing hands-on activities that allow students to engage directly with traditional crafts.*
- *Cultural Immersion: Organizing field trips to museums, artisan workshops, and cultural heritage sites.*
- *Interdisciplinary Integration: Incorporating folk art into various subjects to highlight the interconnectedness of knowledge.*

This essentially expresses visible aesthetic value. The primary goal of artistic education is to shape a person's spiritual culture, familiarize them with universal values, assimilate national cultural heritage, introduce the specific features of work in the field of decorative applied and folk applied art, and develop students' visual abilities, artistic taste, creative imagination, spatial thinking, interest in, and love for visual art.

In conclusion, Folk decorative art is essential in developing students' pedagogical culture in Uzbekistan. Integrating traditional arts into the educational curriculum has enhanced students' cultural identity, aesthetic sensibility, and creative skills. This research highlights the multifaceted benefits of incorporating folk decorative art into education, including preserving and promoting cultural heritage, fostering a deeper connection to cultural roots, and contributing to the holistic development of students.

The study's findings indicate that students who engage with traditional arts develop a stronger sense of cultural identity and pride, show improved aesthetic appreciation, and exhibit enhanced creative thinking and problem-solving skills. These outcomes are achieved through various pedagogical approaches, such as experiential learning, cultural immersion, and interdisciplinary integration [7]. The importance of fostering an appreciation for national artistic and cultural values cannot be overstated, as it lays the foundation for a well-rounded educational experience that prepares students to become culturally aware and creatively skilled individuals.

Based on the findings of this study, the following suggestions are offered to educators and policymakers to enhance the role of folk decorative art in education:

a) Educational institutions should integrate folk decorative art into various subjects beyond the arts, such as history, literature, and social studies. This interdisciplinary approach will help students understand the interconnectedness of knowledge and appreciate the cultural and historical significance of traditional arts.

b) Schools should incorporate hands-on activities, such as pottery making, embroidery, and wood carving, into their curriculum. These activities provide students with direct engagement with traditional crafts, enhancing their fine motor skills, artistic creativity, and appreciation for the meticulous nature of folk art.

c) Field trips to museums, artisan workshops, and historical sites should be regularly organized to provide students with firsthand exposure to the cultural and historical contexts of folk art. These immersive experiences enrich students' understanding and appreciation of traditional art forms.

d) Professional development programs for teachers should include training on how to integrate folk decorative art into their teaching practices effectively. This training will equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to engage students with traditional arts meaningfully.

e) Schools should collaborate with local artisans and cultural institutions to organize workshops, exhibitions, and cultural events. These partnerships can provide valuable resources and expertise, enriching the educational experience for students.

f) Educational authorities should develop and distribute resources, such as textbooks, instructional videos, and lesson plans, that focus on folk decorative art. These resources can support teachers in delivering high-quality art education and ensure that traditional arts are accurately and effectively taught.

g) Regular evaluation of the effectiveness of folk art programs should be conducted to ensure they meet educational goals. Feedback from students and teachers can help refine and improve the integration of traditional arts into the curriculum.

By implementing these suggestions, educators and policymakers can enhance the role of folk decorative art in developing students' pedagogical culture, ensuring that future generations appreciate and preserve their cultural heritage while fostering their creative and aesthetic abilities.

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